

Financial Inclusion and Women Entrepreneurship: The Role of Self-Help Groups in Rural Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Financial inclusion plays crucial role in promoting and developing countries like India. In the form of affordability, accessibility and its availability of the financial inclusion services from banking, credit access, investments and insurance and so on for the underprivileged SHGs women. Financial resources should ensure its own access, which enable the individual and small business to participate and develop the economic activities and overall financial wellbeing.

On the other hand, SHGs development have emerged as a important tool in promoting the financial inclusion especially economically driven women in rural India. They are very small voluntary group of women, having 10 to 20, joins together to pool their savings and access to microcredit. They join and form a platform for their financial empowerment by allowing members collectively to save money, getting collateral free loans, and investing in income generating activities. It also fosters them entrepreneurship, self-reliance among women, that also provided social and economic support to their achievements.

Both the financial inclusion and SHGs are key drivers of economic development, in rural women empowerment. The are very crucial in facilitating and bridging the gap between the financial services for women, that facilitate the access to savings habits, credit and insurance that fosters entrepreneurship also. The study enhances the impacts SHGs rural women on financial inclusion and entrepreneurship in the states like Tamil Nadu. It also explores about the financial accessibility that promotes the business and also contributes to socio-economic development of women.

This research tries to adopt the quantitative analysis through the questionnaire methods from the various active SHGs in Tamil Nadu. The districts including of Salem, Coimbatore and Madurai. The survey was conducted to bring out the insights into the institutional support mechanism. The findings of the study mainly analysed to assess the policy effectiveness in carryout the financial inclusion.

SHGs women who are all the part of validating the higher level of savings pattern, developing financial decision making, enhancing the investment through income generating activities. The research mainly highlights about the microcredit facilities that are providing through the SHGs pointedly contributing to the establishment and expansion of small-scale enterprises and income generating activities that includes tailoring, food processing, agribusiness, organic way of producing goods. The study also reveals the participation of SHGs women confidence level, bargaining power, with all economic developments. The research aims to contribute the wider scope of financial inclusion, empowerment of women, entrepreneurship in rural areas. This empirical proof that ensures the role of SHGs in rural areas of Tamilnadu.

Introduction

Definition and Significance of Financial Inclusion

The availability and accessibility are simply representing the financial inclusion to all individuals, specially economically weakened communities. The people with their income level or geographic location, who utilize the financial services like banking, credit, insurance and the various investments. The objective of nurturing economic participation, which helps the individuals to align with financial risks, increasing the investment decisions.

There are some long remained inaccessible financial systems to huge sections of the society specifically rural population. In the place of financial process, also creates dependency on informal credit sources, sometimes they are characterized by the heavy interest rates and strict repayment ways. The inclusive finance, emerges the fundamental enabler of the socio-economic development. In this environment, financial inclusion appears as a critical enabler of socioeconomic advancement, bringing impoverished groups into the mainstream economy. A well-structured financial system promotes capital development, improves resource allocation, and assures economic stability. In developing economies where gender inequities in financial access remain, concerted measures to promote inclusive banking practices have become critical.

The financial system has been established a fine correlation with poverty alleviation, improved household stability and boosted livelihood opportunities to the inclusion of the women. Many of the research studies access to credit and savings mechanisms allows women to make more educated economic decisions, promoting self-sufficiency. With the independence in financial aspects, negotiating power in the households and its own communities that broader the societal transformation also attains the greater view.

Global level financial institutions, accentuated policies and its initiatives achieves outreach of the financial and banking services.

Self-Help Groups (SHGs) as a Mechanism for Financial Empowerment

The effective grassroots which facilitate the inclusive finance in the SHG model. A voluntary association for SHG of individuals, primarily women who puddle their resources, that creates funds for savings. The groups are formed in the base of the mutual trust, shares the accountability and financial discipline. They regularly contribute funds to common funds, that serves as credit puddle, from which they use to borrow funds in nominal rate of interest, for their generation of income.

Framework of SHGs mainly framed to serve as an intermediary in between financial institutions that bridges the gap raised by socio-economic constraints. By balancing the credibility, the groups have access for institutional credit from microfinance institutions, government grants and banks that do not require the collateral. The approach effectively addressed the obstacles are historically limited to the women from financial channels, like lack of literacy in financial aspects, challenges in documentation and restrictions in movement.

SHGs are always important, and crucial role in providing financial awareness, by contributing the knowledge to the women with the necessary skills to handle both the business and personal finances efficiently. Many of the programs for SHGs were incorporated with training sessions on accounting, concepts of budgets, various pooling investment strategies, digital initiations and handling and optimizing the resources properly. The way also fosters the social capital, to the women who engaged in SHG activities that gives confidence, leadership skills and decisions making skills.

Beyond the financial inclusion, the success of SHGs extends to developmental outcomes,

that includes educational opportunities for the children, updated access to the healthcare, participation in community. The environment of collective responsibility and peer- based learning fosters the groups to create an ecosystem. In that approach, the women actively participate and tries to contribute to the both social and economic growth. The approach is said to holistic where the potential of SHGs in empowering women, thriving community development.

SHGs in India and Tamil Nadu

The witnessed and expansile growth of SHG in India from early inception 1990s. The National Bank of Agriculture and Rural development took initiative to inaugurate the Self-help Group Bank Link Program in the year 1992, that has become one the biggest and largest microfinance network initiatives in the global level. The program has been framed to facilitate the banks loans to SHGs directly, empowering them to become self-reliant in finance. Government agencies, NGOs and Financial institutions were entered into collaborative activities, to energise the program, that results in significant expansion of SHG networks, across India.

In Tamil Nadu, The Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women is playing pivotal role in preceding the SHG network in successful manner. Especially the Mahalir Thittam scheme supporting many SHG women from rural Tamil Nadu, for providing the financial assistance, developing their skills through organised programs that led women empowerment and development. Some the cooperative banks, Rural banks have also extended their credit facilities to these groups.

The SHGs framework of state is being featured by well organised groups that operates all the villages, block, district levels that ensures the streamlined coordination between the activities carried on for better allocation of

resources. SHGs have strengthened more by introducing the Digital Financial inclusion to reach more and more remote regions, e-payment, mobile banking solutions, that enable them to undisturbed financial transactions. Continuous success of the support initiatives underlines, the efficiency of SHGs in nurturing the sustainable economic development at the grassroots level.

Financial Inclusion as a Catalyst for Women Entrepreneurship

An Analysis of critical dimension of financial inclusion led to the development of entrepreneurship that includes the training in vocational, other guiding programs and networking opportunities. Many of SHG linked groups were benefited from the government schemes, receiving subsidies, carrying out the CSR partnerships by providing the technical and logical support. Such incorporating SHGs led many businesses into larger chain business, facilitated with the digital platforms, e-commerce networks that has augmented their fulfilled growth.

The financial inclusion intersection with entrepreneurship has proved record that are transformative to rural development especially rural women. SHGs are serving as incubators for small scale industries, helping and enabling the women to inaugurate the venture with diversified sectors such as agriculture, handicrafts, textiles, food processing and retails. After shifting from the financial dependence to self-sustained economic activities has deep-rooted implications for reducing poverty and development for community. Many studies were undertaken to analyse the women who gain the access to formal financial services shows the higher level of engagement towards entrepreneur, by stabilised business, income stability. The group ability to secure loans with the strict and stringent collateral requirement that empower women to invest in the productive assets, market expansion, and various revenue

streams. The nature of SHGs is there to support the members who can share the business insights, collaborate with others for market driven opportunities and solutions.

Even though there are more advanced techniques and growth are there, there are some more challenges awaiting to ensure the equitable financial access to all the women entrepreneurs. There is very limited exposure to advanced business strategies, with inadequate access to the formal markets, regulatory constraints are continuing have hurdles. These gaps require more attention and multi stakeholder approach that involves policymakers, financial institutions, society, private organisations. Tailormade intrusions, such as targeted financial literacy awareness, digital banking innovations, related market initiatives, are necessary to maximize the potential of SHGs in women's entrepreneurship.

Many microfinances' initiatives based on SHG have been reformed for economic participation among rural women in our country. By giving them access to credit facilities, nurturing business development, motivating socio-economic empowerment have been introduced as a keystone of inclusive growth.

Significance of the Study

The research explores the role of the SHGs in rural Tamil Nadu plays a pivotal role in academic, social and policy implications. Inclusion remains a key determinant for economic development, by understanding the role of the SHGs, by empowering them through financial aspects which is crucial for nurturing sustainable growth in rural women. The study mainly focus on how the SHGs enables the financial access to the rural women in Tamil Nadu. Still women are facing multifaceted problems starting from lack of financial literacy to sociocultural barriers. This study explores such gap by providing the microcredit, savings facilities, and literacy awareness, helps the

women to become independent economically.

Added to the above, the study also tries to analyse the SHG participation of women entrepreneur's actions. By giving access to the credit and training through SHGs women in rural areas are able to inaugurate and expand their business thereby generates the employment opportunities for themselves and dependents. The key significance of the study is to focus regions in Tamil Nadu especially Coimbatore, Trichy and Salem. These districts are playing a crucial role, in rural development. The Findings and Suggestions may help the policymakers, financial institutions, NGOs to design more effectively round out the financial inclusion to be tailored in a way and need of the SHGs

This study on Financial Inclusion and Women Entrepreneurship: The Role of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) in Rural Tamil Nadu holds significant academic, social, and policy implications. As financial inclusion remains a key driver of economic development, understanding the role of SHGs in empowering women through financial access is crucial for fostering sustainable growth in rural areas.

The practical recommendations shall be suggested to face the challenges and identify the opportunities, where it provides the practical views and ideas to improve the financial services, inclusion in digital aspects, market access. The gained insights will help to the wider discourse on Gender empowerment, development of rural, financial inclusion that make valuable for researchers, policymakers and practioners.

Review of Literature

The financial literacy programs play a major role with SHGs development, they also insisted to have financial education that improves the decision-making capacities among SHGs members significantly pointed by Verma (2022). Though there are some regional disparities that are being observed by Sharma and Nair (2023) in their paper, penetration of

SHGs were consistently increased in states like Tamil Nadu and Kerala and successful too. They face challenges in lower level of female involvement and institutional support. They also highlighted that the government policies shall be framed, banking outreach programs shall be organised, are necessary to expand the SHGs financial inclusions all over India. On the other side, Patel and Das (2021) were examined the effectiveness of SHG linkages to improve, financial literacy among rural women. They particularly studied about the how the SHGs are likely to open the bank accounts, access credits from financial institution, their prompt repayments and hurdles facing by them.

Singh and Sharma(2023) in their paper explains in relating with the hurdles, SHGs serves as a critical tool, for enhancing and encouraging, financial inclusion formalisation, financial literacy that leads to wider scope for economic stability. On the flip side Ashwini Pandhare and Praveen Naik Bellampalli (2024) in their paper, another study was undertaken to analyse the impact and intervention of micro financial institutions and their engagement toward entrepreneurship of SHG Women. Finally, they SHGs participation does not only the improved financial access, but also developing the life style, decision making capacities, their social status and overall empowerment that contributes significantly towards poverty alleviation and community development. In an article of World bank. org (Nov 2024) highlighted the other way of emphasizing the SHGs, is to create substantial employment opportunities in rural areas. It is important to untap the potentials of rural entrepreneurs in our country. At the same time Rao and Priya (2022) analysed the increasing women's participation in society development programs. There was significant shifting in various responsibilities

Radha Thangarajan (2024) insisted by joining with more and more members improves

financial stability and awareness of the rural SHGs and their economic status. They are the effective tool that brings relegated society to mainstream by nurturing financial inclusion empowerment. Mishra et al (2022), in their paper, analysed the impact of SHGs participation and found the microfinance entrée which led to increase small-scale business for rural women. They contribute not only to household income but the aim is to create employment for the women. Gupta and Sen (2021), in their paper suggested to introduce the digital marketing mentorship and training programs that could enhance the SHGs entrepreneurship.

Mukherjee and Roy (2021) in their paper explore the development SHGs women participation leads psychological and emotional impact and added their financial independence leads them to be more self-esteemed, having more self-confidence. The above studies mainly insist the multidimensional benefits of SHGs in rural areas in our country. Thus, financial inclusion plays a significant role in improving the SHG participation, institutional inefficiency and financial literacy gaps that are challenging.

After analysing the valuable insights in the role of SHGs in women empowerment and their financial inclusion, there are some of the research gaps identified with the help of the above reviews. Though there are more analysis done in the various districts in Tamil Nadu individually. There are some limited research studies in exploring the digital tools that can enhance financial inclusion for SHG members. Some of the longitudinal studies highlighted some long-term impact of SHG participations in the regions. With the above research gap, this study is being undertaken to analyse the effectiveness of SHGs in rural Tamil Nadu, with women empowerment and financial inclusion.

Objectives of the Study

Based on the significance of the financial inclusion the objectives framed on the basis of

their credit, banking and other services. It aims to evaluate the impact of the SHGs on financial aspects and related business growth among women. The key objectives of the study are:

- To assess the role of SHG women, in promoting financial inclusion in rural areas of Tamil Nadu.
- To examine the impact of SHG women access to credit, savings and other related financial services.
- To study the socio-economic empowerment of women due to their participation in SHGs
- To explore the role of digital financial services and technology in improving financial access for SHG members.

Research Methodology

The research aims to assess the role of the SHGs in promoting their women entrepreneurship and their financial inclusion in rural place of Tamil Nadu. The rural areas in the districts especially cover with the Coimbatore, Salem and Trichy for the study. The research methodology is explained with the systematic way where it explains about the research design, area of the study, sampling techniques and target population.

The study strictly adheres the combination of descriptive and exploratory research design in order to analyse the impact of SHGs. Both of the qualitative and quantitative methods is used to provide for better understanding.

The study area covers three districts in Tamil Nadu, were selected on basis of hub for small-scale industries, known for its SHG growing and rural financial initiatives and self-employment schemes. The districts selected are having socio-economic conditions, entrepreneurial development and financial awareness among SHG members.

The sample size of the 30 respondents is from each of the districts in total of 90 respondents were taken for the study, in representing of SHG women involving in financial activities and entrepreneurship.

Results, Analysis and Interpretation
Correlation Analysis

The study aims to analyse the role of SHGs in financial inclusion and women entrepreneurship in rural districts for tamilnadu. It is highly important to whether long duration of member of SHGs is having impact of awareness in financial related aspects. So it was conducted to to exmaine such relationship between them. The hypothesis are framed according to their impact.

H0 (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant correlation between SHG Membership Duration and Financial Literacy.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant correlation between SHG Membership Duration and Financial Literacy.

Nonparametric Correlations

Correlations			SHG Membership (Years)	Financial Literacy
Spearman's rho	SHG Membership (Years)	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.975**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	Financial Literacy	Correlation Coefficient	.975**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
		N	90	90

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

For the above correlation, spearman correlation was used to examine the relationship between SHGs membership and Financial Literacy. The results shows that there is strong positive correlation between both the variables where it shows $p=0.975$, $p,0.01$ where the correlation is statistically significant at 1% level. It clearly indicates that when there is more SHGs membership and financial literacy also improves accordingly. Hence, Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternate Hypothesis is accepted.

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)

In upcoming opportunities, SHGs is getting developed day by day with the various options. At the end of the day, the revenue generating is key factor for all the investors or business owners though it is small business. Technology with finance plays pivotal role in organising the business particularly in small

and medium enterprises(SMEs) and Self-help groups(SHG). At the same time, comfort in dealing finance is also one of the prima-facie factors that influencing the both business and revenue growth. Analysing by the various levels of digital banking and its comfort towards usage, can provide the valuable insights to generate revenue. To analyse this the following hypothesis framed and analysed using One-way Anova analysis.

H0(Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference in Business Revenue Increase across different levels of Digital Banking Comfort.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference in Business Revenue Increase across different levels of Digital Banking Comfort.

Descriptives

Business Revenue Increase	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Not at all	18	2.00	.000	.000	2.00	2.00	2	2
Slightly	18	2.00	.000	.000	2.00	2.00	2	2
Moderately	18	3.00	.000	.000	3.00	3.00	3	3
Considerably	36	4.50	.007	.003	4.33	4.67	4	5
Total	90	3.20	1.173	.124	2.95	3.45	2	5

ANOVA

Business Revenue Increase	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	113.400	3	37.800	361.200	<.001
Within Groups	9.000	86	.105		
Total	122.400	89			

Multiple Comparisons

Independent Variable	Business Revenue Increase (Dependent Variable)	Comparison	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Business Revenue Increase	Not at all	Slightly	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Moderately	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
Slightly	Not at all	Moderately	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
Moderately	Not at all	Slightly	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
Considerably	Not at all	Slightly	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Moderately	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000
		Considerably	.000	.000	.98	-.000	.000

Homogeneous Subsets

Business Revenue Increase

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

Digital Banking Comfort	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05		
		1	2	3
Not at all	18	2.00		
Slightly	18	2.00		
Moderately	18		3.00	
Considerably	36			4.50
Sig		1.000	1.000	1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.
 a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 20.571.
 b. The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.

Interpretation

Generally, entrepreneurs are comfortable in dealing their finance digitally where there

are quick options of make or receive payments and there is no delay. This highly reduced the dependency factors, faster transactions and better cash flow management shall be done. From the above descriptive results, respondents who rated digital banking comfort as ‘Not at all’, or ‘slightly’ has a revenue at 2.00, whereas those who rated the comfort as ‘considerably’, is having highest mean score to 4.50 that shows as more revenue from business. The F-value is significantly high (361.200) along with the p-value is <0.01, which indicates there is statistically significant difference between two variables business revenue increase with all levels of digital banking comfort.

The Post hoc Tukey test have been done for multiple comparison table that shows the group differences are statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. The mean differences also shows that those respondents who says ‘considerably’ is having more business revenue growth. The homogeneous subset analysis shows that each of the subset respondents are significantly different revenue that varies with other subsets.

There are some possible reasons for the business revenue increase due to digital banking comfort. The reasons are

1. The SHGs members are comfortable in paying their transactions for quick transfers and transactions.
2. They feel it reduces the dependency on physical banking activities and cash flow management.
3. They can able to learn about the digital banking tools, for better decision making.
4. Through this digital banking, it eliminates the physical visit to banks is reducing, that reduces the transportation and other administrative costs.
5. For better financial tracking, timely decision making and secure transactions are leading to stable revenue and growth in business. The One-way Anova results highlighted

that there is strong connection between digital banking comfort and business revenue growth. Hence, Null Hypothesis is rejected and Alternative Hypothesis is accepted. This clearly indicates that There is a significant difference in Business Revenue Increase across different levels of Digital Banking Comfort.

Multiple Regression Analysis

H0 (Null Hypothesis): SHG Support (Loans, Savings, Training) does not significantly predict Business Skills Development.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): SHG Support (Loans, Savings, Training) significantly predicts Business Skills Development.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Business Training, Microloans, Savings Support, Business Support		Enter

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	1.000	.000

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	72.000	3	24.000		
	Residual	.000	98	.000		
	Total	72.000	101			

SHGs plays a pivotal role in developing inclusive finance and women empowerment. Especially, the SHGs members are from marginalised communities and as a small entrepreneur. SHGs, generally aims to enhance the business skills set development, providing financial services like loans, savings and related training programs to enhance the sustainable entrepreneurship and grow economically. It is essential to study such various services are having significant impact on business growth among SHG members. To assess such impact of such SHG support in the form of microloans, savings and training with business skills development. This analysis helps to analyse and predict the improvements in business skills among SHG members.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.000	.000		
	Microloans	.000	.000	.000	
	Savings Support	1.000	.000	1.000	
	Business Training	.000	.000	.000	

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	3.00	5.00	4.00	.000	99
Std. Predicted Value	-1.112	1.112	.000	1.000	99
Standard Error of Predicted Value	.000	.000	.000	.000	99
Adjusted Predicted Value	3.00	5.00	4.00	.000	99
Residual	.000	.000	.000	.000	99
Std. Residual					9
Std. Deleted Residual					9
Deleted Residual	.000	.000	.000	.000	99
Std. Deleted Residual					9
Wald's Distance	1.318	3.958	2.987	.979	99
Cook's Distance					9
Centered Leverage Value	.011	.044	.033	.011	99

Interpretation

The results of regression analysis are indicating a perfect fit, by examining the relationship between the business skills and SHG support(training, loans, and savings). It is evidenced that R Square of 1.000 which means that variances of business skills are matching with the predictor variables. Adjusted R2 of 1.000 for further supports, the idea that adding predictors, which does not include complexity or noise. Hence, the model perfectly business skills development, which is usual in data.

With analysing of Anova table, the sum of squares for regression is 72.000, with the residual sum of squares of 0.000.Since there is no error in prediction, the model fits the data perfectly.

The point is intercept in predictor variable business skills that is valued in 0. Microloans and business training has no independent contribution whereas the saving support perfectly determines the business skills. Microloans and business training is having coefficients of 0, it is implied that there is no statistical effect, when support on savings is added. The indication shows the possible collinearity, it is savings support is highly correlated with other predictors, allowing them independent that are undetectable.

The model shows a strong predictive relationship between Business Skills

developments and SHG support. Savings appears to be the sole determinant of business skills, whereas microloans and training do not contribute to the development of business skills. In the model, all the residuals are at zero which is extremely rare. It is clearly identified at dependent variable is a direct function of one of the predictors, where there is perfect collinearity between the independent variables.

Findings

Some of the other findings,

- The maximum respondents belong to age between 25 to 30 years that implies youngsters are showing interest for the SHG business growth.
- It is implied that maximum number of respondents have completed their primary education at the minimum.
- 40% of the respondents are salaried or job worker, as they may another income the SHG business.
- Maximum number of respondents are having knowledge to the greater extent in the SHG.
- Most of the members of SHG attends the meetings Monthly.
- 40% of the members are using the Microloan as financial services to the great extent, at the same time some of them hesitates to attend business meetings.
- More than 50% of the SHG members are having business skills.
- Nearly 55% of the SHG members having efficiency in managing the business finances

Suggestions

Financial inclusion and women empowerment are interconnected pillars of the economic development. Especially framed for the rural and marginalised women, with aim of the empowering them financially, decision making ability by promoting more entrepreneurship opportunities, contributing on overall economic growth. This study

undertaken to analyse the women empowerment and their inclusive finance ability by taking Trichy, Coimbatore and Salem districts SHG members. Various factors and points have been analysed with the help of questionnaire from rural area SHG members of these 3 cities. The study revealed many aspects, things need to be improved or altered.

The below are the suggestions for further upgradation and development of Self-Help Group women in rural areas.

1. About 40% of the respondents having more financial awareness, there is a room for further development of other SHG members, where this 40% of the long term SHG members shall mentor the other members.
2. Digital banking usage shall be given to SHG members by introducing them with usage of mobile banking, payments in online and other payment literacy awareness.
3. Business training is distributed unevenly, where the training for different skill levels shall be given and improve overall the business sustainability.
4. The SHG members, shall be asked to utilise micro loans effectively more and educate the other members to proper utilization of the loan amount properly
5. Most of the respondents are meeting at different interval time, by regularising the best practice of attending the meeting would enhance the business skills, and other aspects SHG.
6. Mentorship programs shall be organized and encourage peer-to-peer learning in between experienced and newly joined members.
7. SHG members shall be educated with various structured savings schemes for themselves in the form of RDs, FDs, that will boost their self-sufficiency.
8. Further longitudinal studies shall be done along only with barriers, impact of SHG entrepreneurship in between states shall be done future studies.

Conclusion

The study that analyses the role of SHG rural women in financial inclusion and women empowerment aspects would be great and more successful if some of the minor changes or issues were overcome regularly. The analysis reveals that the insights of financial awareness, SHG members' income level, training in business needs, and their active participation. The noteworthy part of the respondents exhibits their awareness and commitments in SHG activities, even though there are notable gaps in the areas of digital banking comfort, decision making, income growth and support for their savings. These challenges are to be addressed, by fixing targets and streamlining, improving access to microfinance, decision making in finances, augmenting the SHG meeting structures who can further contribute to economic stability and self-sufficiency. Incorporating these strategies and developments, SHGs shall increase their impact, that leads to higher the financial inclusion level and long sustainability for their SHG Members. Efforts in policy refinement, adaptation of technologies, and collaboration with institutions, that is important to continue the financial inclusion to aid for transformative version of economic development of women.

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